

PHARMACOECONOMIC BURDEN AND COST-REDUCTION IMPACT OF PHARMACIST-LED BRAND SUBSTITUTION IN HYPERTENSION MANAGEMENT: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY FROM PAKISTAN

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Abstract

To evaluate the pharmacoeconomic burden of antihypertensive therapy and assess the cost-saving impact of pharmacist-led brand substitution among patients in Abbottabad, Pakistan. This descriptive cross-sectional study included 120 hypertensive patients from clinical settings in Abbottabad. Data on demographics, comorbidities, and prescribed antihypertensive regimens were collected. Monthly medication costs were calculated using market prices. Pharmacists then identified lower-cost alternatives with equivalent dosage and therapeutic value. Cost differences pre- and post-substitution were analyzed. Patients were predominantly aged 51–60 years, with a slight male predominance. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, and dyslipidemia were common comorbidities. Most patients were prescribed diuretics, beta-blockers, vasodilators, or ACE inhibitors. The average monthly cost of anti-hypertensive medication was PKR 2,444. After pharmacist-led substitution, 65% of patients fell into the lowest cost category (PKR 0–300), compared to 21.7% before intervention. Cost savings ranged from 50% to 70% per patient. Antihypertensive pharmacotherapy imposes a considerable financial burden in Pakistan. Pharmacist-led brand substitution significantly reduces medication costs, improving affordability without compromising efficacy. These findings support policy reforms to empower pharmacists and encourage rational generic prescribing in similar low-resource settings.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension, a leading modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular and renal diseases, affects over 1 billion individuals globally and is projected to increase by approximately 60% by 2025.¹ In Pakistan, the burden is particularly acute, with a significant portion of healthcare expenditures—over 60%—borne out-of-pocket (OOP) by households, and medications accounting for more than half of these costs.² This financial strain often leads patients to forgo essential antihypertensive treatments, exacerbating health disparities and increasing the risk of uncontrolled blood pressure.³

The pharmacoeconomic burden is further intensified by the wide cost variation among antihypertensive drugs of the same strength and dosage form. Studies have highlighted significant price differences between branded and generic medications, with some generics offering the same therapeutic efficacy at a fraction of the cost.⁴ Despite the availability of these cost-effective alternatives, patients often remain on more expensive branded medications, primarily due to a lack of awareness or guidance.¹

Pharmacists, as accessible healthcare professionals, are uniquely positioned to mitigate this economic burden through brand substitution practices. Their role extends beyond dispensing medications to include patient education, therapeutic counseling, and cost-effective drug selection.⁵ In countries like Canada and Japan, pharmacist-led interventions have demonstrated substantial cost savings and improved health outcomes in hypertension management.^{6,7} These interventions not only reduce medication costs but also enhance patient adherence and satisfaction.^{8,9}

However, the practice of brand substitution by pharmacists varies globally, influenced by regulatory frameworks and healthcare policies.¹⁰ In some regions, pharmacists are authorized to substitute brands without prior physician approval, while in others, such practices are restricted. In Pakistan, the potential of pharmacists to alleviate the pharmacoeconomic burden remains underutilized, necessitating

policy reforms and professional training to empower pharmacists in this role.¹¹

This study aims to evaluate the impact of pharmacist-led brand substitution on the pharmacoeconomic burden of antihypertensive therapy in Pakistan. By assessing cost variations and patient outcomes associated with brand substitution, the research seeks to inform healthcare policies and optimize hypertension management strategies.

Methodology

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the pharmacoeconomic burden of antihypertensive medications on patients and to evaluate the potential impact of pharmacist-led brand substitution as a cost-reducing strategy. The study was carried out over a period of three months, from **February to April 2021**, at a tertiary care hospital in **Abbottabad, Pakistan**. Approval for the study was granted by the Ethical Review Committee of the Department of Pharmacy, COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus (Reference number: FA16-PHM-060/ATD; Date: 18-1-2021).

Study Population and Sampling

The study population included hypertensive patients of both genders, aged 18 years or above, who were either newly diagnosed or receiving ongoing antihypertensive treatment during the data collection period. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was employed to collect data from patients' records and medical charts. Patients whose prescriptions were directly influenced by senior consultants or specialized therapeutic committees were excluded to reduce bias and ensure analysis of routine pharmacotherapy practices.

Data Collection Tools and Procedure

Patient data were extracted from patients' records and medical charts, using a standardized data collection form designed for this study. This form captured the following variables:

- **Demographic data:** age, gender, BMI

- **Clinical details:** type of hypertension, comorbidities, prescribed antihypertensive medications, strength, dosage form
- **Pharmacoeconomic data:** brand name, manufacturer, price per unit, total monthly cost of antihypertensive therapy
- **Availability of alternative lower-cost brands** with identical strength and dosage form
- **Patient adherence** as recorded in medical notes or pharmacy refill records

To ensure reliable economic comparisons, the price data were gathered from hospital pharmacy records, local drug registries, and verified with the Drug Regulatory Authority of Pakistan (DRAP) and Pharmacy Council Pakistan's approved price lists.

Evaluation of Pharmacoeconomic Burden and Brand Substitution

The monthly cost burden of each patient's antihypertensive regimen was calculated and compared with the lowest-priced available alternatives of the same generic drug, strength, and dosage form. The potential cost savings through pharmacist-recommended brand **Results**

Of the 120 hypertensive patients analyzed, 63 (52.5%) were male and 57 (47.5%) were female. The age distribution indicated that the majority were between 51-60 years (36 patients; 30%), followed by 61-70 years (28 patients; 23%), and 41-50 years (21 patients; 18%). The detailed results are given in table 1.

substitution were then estimated. The study also documented instances where brand substitution was implemented by pharmacists and the resulting cost difference.

Pharmacotherapy Assessment

To guide appropriate therapeutic evaluation, the following standard resources were used:

- British National Formulary (BNF)
- JNC-8 hypertension guidelines
- American Heart Association (AHA) journals
- Medscape, Drugs.com, Pharma Guide of Pakistan and relevant literature accessed through Google Scholar

These sources helped validate whether the prescribed medications adhered to evidence-based treatment protocols and to determine the clinical acceptability of suggested lower-cost alternatives.

Data Analysis

Collected data were entered and cleaned using Microsoft Excel® 2021 and subsequently analyzed using IBM SPSS® version 26 for descriptive statistics of different variables.

Table 1: Distribution of study population by gender and age group

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n = 120)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	63	52.5
	Female	57	47.5
Age (years)	21 - 30	3	2
	31 - 40	15	13
	41 - 50	21	18
	51 - 60	36	30
	61 - 70	28	23
	71 - 80	13	11
	81 - 90	4	3

The most frequent BMI group having Hypertension was of normal weighted (male: 33.3% and female: 34.2%) and over-weighted (male: 18.3% and female: 12.5%) (Table 2). The Hypertension were also categorized into different categories on the basis of JNC-8 classification of hypertension. The most frequent category was stage-2 hypertension of SBP (Male: 21.67% and Female: 22.50%) and stage-1 hypertension of DBP for Male (20.0%) and stage-2 for Female (20.0%) (Table 2).

Table 2: BI categories of male and female

	Male	Female
BMI	n (%)	n (%)
Underweight	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Normal Weight	40 (33.3)	41 (34.2)
Overweight	22 (18.3)	15 (12.5)
Obesity	1 (0.8)	1 (0.8)
SBP Categories		
Normal	14 (11.67)	10 (8.33)
Elevated	7 (5.83)	7 (5.83)
Stage 1	16 (13.33)	9 (7.50)
Stage 2	26 (21.67)	27 (22.50)
Hypertensive Crisis	0 (0)	4 (3.33)
DBP Categories		
Normal	20 (16.67)	14 (11.67)
Elevated	0 (0)	0 (0)
Stage 1	24 (20.00)	19 (15.83)
Stage 2	19 (15.83)	24 (20.00)
Hypertensive Crisis	0 (0)	0 (0)

The most frequently prescribed antihypertensive classes were diuretics (51 patients; 43%), beta blockers (49 patients; 41%) and vasodilator (33 patients; 28%). ACE inhibitors were used by 18% of patients, ARBs by 16%, CCBs by 10%, and only 2% received ARAs. Common co-prescribed medications included statins (66%), antiplatelets (57%), and anticoagulants (42%) (table 3)

Table 3: Classes of antihypertensive agents and frequently co-prescribed medications

Medication Class	Frequency (n = 120)	Percentage (%)
Vasodilators	33	28
Diuretics	51	43
Beta blockers	49	41
ACE inhibitors (ACEIs)	22	18
Angiotensin Receptor Blockers (ARBs)	19	16
Calcium Channel Blockers (CCBs)	12	10
Aldosterone Receptor Antagonists (ARAs)	2	2
Statins	79	66
Antiplatelets	68	57
Anticoagulants	50	42
Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs)	33	28
Antidiabetic Agents	32	27

Anti-anginal	47	39
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The average total monthly cost for all medications was PKR 2,444.45, with a minimum of PKR 268.00 and a maximum of PKR 8,469.00. The distribution of patients across different cost ranges is shown in Figure 1 below. This wide range indicates substantial

variability in individual patient costs, likely driven by differences in the number and type of medications prescribed. Table 4 showed the distribution of patients across cost-of-therapy categories (all medications combined).

Figure 1: Distribution of patients across different cost ranges

Monthly Cost (PKR)	Frequency (n = 120)	Percentage (%)
0 - 1,000	23	19
1,001 - 2,000	50	42
2,001 - 3,000	21	18
3,001 - 4,000	6	5
4,001 - 5,000	4	3
5,001 - 6,000	6	5
6,001 - 7,000	5	4
7,001 - 8,000	2	2
8,001 - 9,000	2	2

To isolate the monthly costs specifically for antihypertensive medications, we calculated each patient’s monthly antihypertensive cost and categorized them. A comparison of patient distribution across cost categories before and after pharmacist-led brand substitution demonstrates significant cost savings. After substitution, a large proportion of patients shifted to the lowest cost brane range (0–300 PKR) (Table 5).

Cost Range (PKR)	Prescribed Brand (n = 120)	Altered Brand (n = 120)
0 - 300	26	78

301 - 600	49	27
601 - 900	21	9
901 - 1,200	9	3
1,201 - 1,500	5	2
1,501 - 1,800	4	1
1,801 - 2,100	4	0
2,101 - 2,400	2	0

Discussion:

This study investigated the demographic, clinical, pharmacotherapeutic, and pharmaco-economic characteristics of 120 hypertensive patients in Abbottabad, Pakistan, and evaluated the impact of pharmacist-led brand substitution on antihypertensive costs.

Demographically, our study population (52.5% males, 47.5% females) mirrors the World Health Organization's observation that hypertension tends to be more prevalent among males, especially in middle and old age. The age distribution, peaking at 51–60 years (30%), corresponds to epidemiological trends reported in South Asia, where hypertension incidence significantly increases after the age of 50.^{12,13} This age-associated pattern underscores the need for strategic intervention, as older patients often present with comorbidities that complicate both pharmacotherapy and economic management. Comorbid conditions were common: diabetes mellitus occurred in a large fraction of patients, in line with regional trends. Indeed, nearly half of hypertensive South Asians have concurrent diabetes, and Aslam *et al.* (2018) observed that most patients with longstanding hypertension “had mostly developed diabetes”.¹³ Obesity was also prevalent and strongly associated with hypertension in Pakistan; one study found 70% of hypertensive patients were obese (BMI>23), with higher obesity rates in women than men.¹⁴ Clinically, most patients in our study presented with long-standing, uncontrolled hypertension; a substantial proportion had severe (stage 2) hypertension at diagnosis. This is similar to other Pakistani reports where a majority of emergency patients had uncontrolled blood pressure with frequent hypertensive crises.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

The cost of antihypertensive therapy was a major concern in our study, reflecting the high out-of-pocket (OOP) burden in Pakistan. Multiple analyses confirm that medication costs dominate hypertension expenditures in South Asia. In Pakistan an estimated 60% of all healthcare spending is borne by patients,¹⁷ and antihypertensive drugs constitute the largest component. A Karachi cost-of-illness study found that drug expenses made up ~60% of the total treatment cost for both Stage-1 and Stage-2 hypertension.¹³ Similarly, our data showed that patients paid thousands of rupees per month for medications alone, often straining household budgets. These findings align with an earlier Karachi survey which concluded that antihypertensive therapy “imposed a high burden on the pocket of [the] common man” and was a major cause of non-adherence.¹³ Globally, hypertension is known to incur immense costs: total costs per patient have been estimated at US\$630 (direct and indirect) on average, translating into annual per-capita expenditures far exceeding most patients' means.¹⁸ In low-income settings, the trend is worsening; one systematic review noted accelerating hypertension costs worldwide.¹⁸ Our cost results also showed that branded products and combinations greatly increased expenses. We found that prescribing decisions significantly affected affordability: branded generics of popular drugs could cost 3–4 times more than unbranded generics. This is consistent with reports that Pakistani clinicians often favor originator or high-priced generic brands.¹⁴ For example, despite evidence that simple thiazides are equally effective, high-end branded ACEIs were common in many regimens. Such practices amplify the financial

burden.¹³ It follows that enhancing generic use is critical for reducing costs.

Pharmacists have an underutilized but potentially powerful role in mitigating this economic burden. Evidence from other countries shows that pharmacist-led management (including counseling, adherence support, and medication review) substantially improves hypertension outcomes.^{19,20} Importantly, pharmacists tend to have more knowledge about bioequivalence and generics than physicians. Toverud *et al.* (2015) found pharmacists worldwide are aware of generics' cost-saving potential, and in high-resource settings they readily dispense generics to all patients.²¹ In Pakistan, however, trust in generic quality is mixed and price regulation is imperfect. The recent editorial by Abdullah *et al.* (2024) explicitly calls for greater generic prescribing to improve affordability in Pakistan.¹⁷

Our study underscores the opportunity for pharmacist-driven generic substitution. If pharmacists actively switched patients from expensive brands to low-cost generics, drug costs could drop markedly. Indeed, international analyses estimate that replacing high-cost generics with cheaper equivalents (of equal clinical value) can save 50–90% on drug spending.^{17,21} In our setting, routine substitution (when therapeutically appropriate) could immediately reduce monthly drug bills. To achieve this, pharmacists would need to educate both prescribers and patients about generic efficacy – addressing some of the mistrust noted in emerging economies.²¹ Successful models exist: in countries with mature generic markets, pharmacists automatically dispense the lowest-priced equivalent unless restricted, dramatically lowering costs. Adapting such policies in Pakistan (for example, enforcing laws that require pharmacists to offer the cheapest generic) is advocated in the literature.

Conclusion:

this study highlights the significant pharmaco-economic burden associated with antihypertensive therapy in Pakistan and underscores the role of pharmacist-led brand

substitution in reducing medication costs. Our findings contribute to the growing body of evidence advocating for enhanced pharmacist integration into hypertension management. Policymakers should leverage this potential by reforming substitution laws and improving generic drug accessibility. Such initiatives have the potential to improve therapeutic adherence, reduce healthcare inequities, and ultimately enhance outcomes for hypertensive patients in resource-limited settings.

Limitations:

Despite its strengths, including prospective data collection, methodology, and a well-defined patient population, this study has several limitations. First, it was conducted at a single center, potentially limiting generalizability. Second, long-term adherence and clinical outcomes following cost reduction were not evaluated. Future research should include multi-center studies with longitudinal follow-up to assess the sustained impact of pharmacist-led interventions on blood pressure control and cardiovascular risk reduction.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval

The IRB approval was taken from the Department of Pharmacy, COMSATS University, Abbottabad (Reference number: FA16-PHM-060/ATD, Date: 18-1-2021).

Authors' Contribution

- **Saqib Khan:** Review and editing, Design and drafting of research work, acquisition, compilation and analysis of data, financial resource and manuscript writing.
- **Aysha Mushtaq:** Formal analysis, manuscript writing and acquisition, compilation and analysis of data.

- **Muhammad Ahsan Khan, Muhammad Mehmood Moin ul Haq, Aneela Tahir:** Manuscript writing and acquisition, compilation and analysis of data.

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